

DYNAMICS OF INDIA–NIGERIA DEVELOPMENT ASSISTANCE: MOTIVES, MODALITIES, AND EFFECTS

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18484016>

Abstract: Nigeria–India relations are rooted in their shared historical experience of British colonial domination, which created early political, economic, and socio-cultural linkages even before both states attained independence. This study examines the evolution of India’s development assistance to Nigeria since the Cold War, focusing on the patterns, underlying motives, and developmental impacts of this engagement. Using historical and qualitative methods, the paper traces the foundations of bilateral relations to colonial-era interactions, including Indian migration to British territories such as Nigeria, which facilitated early commercial and social networks. The study further analyzes how India’s foreign policy objectives, South–South cooperation framework, and strategic economic interests have shaped its development assistance to Nigeria. Findings indicate that India’s engagement has expanded across key sectors such as capacity building, education, health, information technology, and infrastructure, contributing to Nigeria’s human capital development and institutional strengthening. However, the paper also highlights challenges relating to sustainability, coordination, and the limited visibility of some assistance programs. The study concludes that India’s development assistance represents an important dimension of Nigeria–India relations and underscores the need for deeper institutional collaboration and policy coherence to maximize developmental outcomes.

Keywords: India–Nigeria relations; Development assistance; South–South cooperation; Foreign policy; Post–Cold War era

Introduction

The fact that Nigeria and India both experienced the same colonial domination from one colonial power–Britain suggests that relations between Nigeria and India predate their political independence. Colonialism laid foundation for the relations of the two countries. Anirudha (1979 :264) asserts that about five millions Indians migrated to different British Colonial territories including Nigeria. This was as a result of indentured labor. This indicated the beginning of an informal relationship between the two countries. Elements like the English language, governmental procedures, and common conviction, have continued to take the two countries into mutual interaction and cooperation (Badejo, 1989:405).

During this time India relations with Nigeria was based on ideological and idealistic principles and

primarily political (Bhattacharya, 2010: 67). Following the collapse of the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics of Russia (USSR) and a serious crisis of national balance of payments, India embarked on pro-market economic reforms in 1991 (Bajpai, 2002:1). The reforms that , opening up the economy to trade and foreign investments (Ahluwalia, 1994:1). These economic policy reforms ended in making the Indian economy stronger than before, as a result of this it has become necessary for India to look for oversea markets, energy and raw materials for its fast growing economy. As a result of this, India has shifted from the policy of ideological and idealistic to more realistic policies that attract investment and trading interactions with African countries, particularly Nigeria. India has its attention in Nigeria for its energy (oil) as well as markets for

its manufactured goods and also for investment opportunities for its companies (Osondu-otti, 2016: 68-96). Therefore, this paper focused on India development aid relations with Nigeria in the post cold war era, especially from the period of the return of democratic rule in Nigeria from 1999 to 2007.

Conceptual Clarification

Development aid is the term generally used to refer to different types of assistance given by one nation to another in form of donations. Morgenthau (1962) defined development aid as the transfer of finance, goods and services from one country to another. Development aid is a veritable tool for supporting education, health, technology, public infrastructure development, agriculture and rural development (Amassoma & Mbah, 2014:107). Similarly, Bakare (2011) states that development aid is the way of increasing the capital available for business investment and economic growth needed to eradicate poverty and uplift the standard of living of the recipient countries. In addition, Ahrjo (2016) expatiates further that foreign direct investment (FDI) as one of the components of development aid, serves as a potential means of transfer of knowledge and technology, creation of job opportunities, increase productivity and entrepreneurship which in return lead to the eradication of poverty through economic growth.

According to Ukpong (2017), development aid can be in form of economic aid such as investment in the economy of the needy country, loans, infrastructural development, he expatiates further that development aid can also be in form of military aid like a supply of military hardware at subsidized rates; and supply of military-technical aid such as military presence to a country in conflict or war with another. Todaro (2010) categorized development aid into three namely; bilateral, multilateral, and private; bilateral development aid is the financial transfer from one country to another, it consists of 60% of development aid to developing nations. Bilateral aid can be

categorized into four forms: development loan, which is repayable within long-term period, technical assistance including technological and managerial experts and transfer of technology, and military assistance, while multilateral aid is the capital outflow from international financial organizations like the World Bank, International Monetary Fund (IMF), trans-national corporations, and commercial banks to developing countries. Ukpong (2017) posits that multilateral aid carries 40% of the global development assistances developing nations. Easterly (2006) defines development aid as the unforced transfer of resources from one country to another with the objective of benefiting the country receiving the aid (governments of developed countries to the governments of underdeveloped countries).

Development Assistance Committee (DAC) of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) defined development aid as financial flows, technical assistance and commodities that are (a) are given by the authorized department of the donor country, (b) with the main aim of promotions of economic development and welfare of recipient country, excluding assistance for military and another non-development purpose, (c) are given as a grants or concessional loans with a grant element equal to at least 25 percent of the total (ALI & Zeb, 2016:108). It is now clear that the main aim of various forms of development aid given to African countries by developed nations is to stimulate social and economic development of the African countries and also to meet the political, security, and the commercial interests of donors.

Theoretical Framework Dependency and underdevelopment theory

Dependency and underdevelopment theory is predicated on the belief that for one to understand the relationship between developing and developed countries, consideration must be given to other global interdependences. The proponents of the theory are the scholars of the Marxist school of thought.

The Marxist school of thought can be traced to the works of Karl Marx and Friedrich Engels. Their ideas, concept, and theories became the foundations of a doctrine which is now known as Marxism. Marx and Engels in mid 1840s wrote that capitalist globalization was gravely eroding the foundations of the international system of states, as a result conflict and competition between nation states had not yet stopped in their belief, but the culpability in future viewed certain to revolve around the two main social classes; the national bourgeoisie, which controlled different system of government, and increasingly sophisticated proletariat (Linklater, 2005:110).

In the early twentieth century Marxist scholars, such as Lenin Stalin, Mao and Castro were able to make their own contribution to the development of Marxist revolutionary approach in a distinctive perspective (McLeans, 1996:312-313). Lenin (1968) and Bukharin (1971) developed the theory of imperialism to explain how expansion of capitalism was responsible for the First World War. They argued that the cause of the war was as a result of the quest for new outlets for surplus capital accumulated by dominant capitalist countries (Linklater, 2005:121). This new conditions of global economic productions, imperialism, colonialism, and globalization relationship between capitalist and pre-capitalists nations would give rise to new types of society, that it is uncertain whether the classical Marxism of Marx and Engels can be used without sweeping changes of emphasis (McLean, 1996:312-314). This led to the theories of dependency and underdevelopment in the late twentieth century.

Historically, dependency and underdevelopment theory can be traced to the writings of the United Nations Economic Commission for Latin America (ECLA) Under the Leadership of Economist Raul Prebisch (1948) that were among the scholars that link underdevelopment to unpleasant terms of international trade (Nyang-oro, 1989:76). They observed that the relationship between

underdeveloped countries and developed countries had deteriorated because of the exploitative nature of the interactions between the two worlds (Agubamah, 2014:65)

Andre-Gunder Frank (1969) one of the proponents of dependency and underdevelopment theory he stated that, lack of development of the Third World countries was as a result of exploitation of the developing countries by the developed world during and after the colonial rule. In his view developing countries (satellites) are incorporated in the international capitalist system that favour the developed countries (metro poles) to the disadvantage of the developing states (satellites) which exist mainly to fulfill the needs of the developed states (metro poles), by extracting resources from the developing state through unequal trade relationship. Frank arrived at this by analyzing how Latin America resources have been exploited by the developed capitalist states.

The dependency and underdevelopment theory emanated from the Latin America, but the framework has been adopted by various scholars of African such as Leys, 1975, Shivji; 1976, Ominde, 1982, Langdon, 1981, Amin, 1974, 1979, Rodney, 1972, Ake, 1981 etc. to analyze the relationship of Africa countries with the Western capitalist countries right from the slave trade period to the present neo-colonialism period has been the genesis of Africa underdevelopment and unfair trade relationship up till date (Nyangoro, 1989:78). According to Rodney (1972), underdevelopment manifests when the basic needs are not equally accessible to all members of the society. That underdevelopment is not the absence of development rather, the unequal nature of human social, political and economic development.

Amin (1977) opened that the law of value that runs at the global level allows the extraction of the value produced in peripheries to the centres. This leads to unequal exploitation and unequal exchange relations between the centres and the peripheries. To Amin, this

unequal exchange relation is the cause of underdevelopment of Third World countries. Dependency and underdevelopment theory is an approach or social science tool of explanation that was predicated on the belief that resources from a “periphery” of poor and underdeveloped countries are used to serve a “core” wealthiest state, thus making the latter rich at the expense of the former (Agubamah, 2014:63). Here, Nigeria is a poor country within the periphery while India as a “core” country within the periphery. Dependency is a situation whereby a certain group of countries have their economy controlled by the development and expansion of another whereby the former is a subject (Daniel, 1980:3). Therefore, this theory will help us to explain the developmental partnership of Nigeria and India.

The Nature of India’s Development Aid Relations with Nigeria after the 1990s Economic Reforms

India’s interaction with Africa (Nigeria inclusive) after independence was based on ideological and idealistic principles and was primarily political (Bhattacharya,2010:67).Following the collapse of the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics (USSR) and a serious crisis of national balance of payments, India embarked on pro-market economic policy reforms in 1991 (Bajpai: 2002:1) .The reforms that opening up the economy to trade and foreign investments (Ahluwalia 1994:1).These economic policy reforms ended in making the Indian economy stronger than before; as a result of this it has become necessary for India to look for oversea markets, energy and raw materials for its fast growing economy.

As a result of this, India has shifted from the policy of ideological and idealistic to more realistic policies that attract investment and trading interactions with African countries particularly Nigeria. India has its attention in Nigeria for its energy (oil) as well as markets for its manufactured goods and also for investment opportunities for its companies (Osondu – Oti, 2016:68-96).

With India’s economic reform and positive growth and the return of Nigeria to civilian rule in 1999, a new impetus was observed in India –Nigeria development relations .As president Olusegun Obasanjo assumed office, he embarked on image laundering and canvassing for foreign direct investment in order to develop the country dilapidated infrastructure after sixteen (16) years of military regimes, and India was one of the countries that the president visited in the year 2000 to solicit for investments (Osondu Oti 2015:114).In justifying his trip to overseas, president Obasanjo stated that:

“As many of you are aware, I have devoted much time and energy journeying to virtually all corners of the globe in my personal efforts to positively reintegrate our country into the international community and attract investment. We are happy to report that the results from these trips have been encouraging enough to confirm my personal belief and the advice of marketing experts, namely that personal contact is the best way to market your product. And my product is Nigeria” (Cited in Oyedoyin, 2002).

In April 2000 the Indian government reciprocated Obasonjo’s visit when the country’s minister for External Affairs Singh visited Nigeria. During the visit the following agreements were reached: Nigerian joint commission was reactivated, which had been kept in Limbo since 1991. The revival of \$ 85 million aid that Indian authorities had voted for Nigeria to enhance the revitalization of the Nigerian machine tools industry at Osogbo. India’s provisional assistance to Nigeria to cover installation, upgrading and rehabilitation of small and medium sized enterprises in the areas of engineering, tool manufacturing, leather technology, weaving and textiles, medicine, woodwork, bio-gas and metal (Punch,2000). Nigeria’s supply of crude oil to India on a long-term basis, as these exports would go a long way to ensure an effective balance of trade between the two countries. Nigeria’s supply of about 25

percent of crude oil to India .This supply rate, which has amounted to over 3.66 million barrels per month and 43.98 million annually, has made India’s direct government to government crude oil contract with the Nigerian Natural Petroleum Corporation (NNPC) the fourth largest of such contracts. In addition the two countries agreed to boost their relations regarding power, steel, railway, telecommunication, medium – sized enterprises (The Guardian 2000)

In a nutshell, the visits by Nigerian president Obasanjo in November 2004 and that of Indian Prime Minister Manmohan Singh in 2007 opened a new page in the two countries development aid relations.This made India oil companies participated in Nigeria bid rounds in 2005-2007 and won 6 oil bloc’s in November2005, an inter-ministerial task force of the government of India visited Nigeria for an official discussion. At the end of discussion, a Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) was signed between Nigerian government and India’s Oil and Natural Gas Corporation (ONGC) Videsh limited, and other India private companies including Essar, Sterling Group, and Sandesara. Also ONGC Mittal Energy Limited (OMEL) entered into a \$ 6 billion infrastructure agreement with Nigeria in exchange for two offshore acreages and oil exploration rights (Naidu, 2010:37).This investment by India was termed “aid for oil strategy”.

The essence of the agreement was for sourcing of 450,000 barrels pay day (BPD) of equity oil and 200.00 BPD equity gas (Totaling 650: BPD oil +oil equivalent and gas equivalent to 35.5 MT) per year over 25 years. Besides India agreed to establish a 2000 mw thermal power plant a refiner and upgrade railway lines in Nigeria (Obi, 2009).

This made India oil companies participated in Nigeria bid rounds in 2005-2007 and won six (6) oil blocks (OPL 279,285 and OPL 297), sterling two (OPL 2005

and OPL 2006), Essar got one (OPL 226).Also in May 2007, in the upstream sector, ONGC Videsh, (OVL) won a 15% stake in block II of the joint development zone (IDZ) of Nigeria and Sao Tome principle.In May 2005 an Indian oil corporation and Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC) agreed on a contract for NNPC supply 40,000 (BPD to 10c, however, at the end of 2007, the contract supply was scaled up to 60,000 BPDC Bevi, 2010:905).The Indian’s oil companies that gained contracts to participate in upstream and refining sectors of Oil and Gas have been involved in the rehabilitation and maintenance of Port Harvourt and Warri oil refineries through the provision of technical manpower and training of Nigeria engineers. In addition, India became instrumental in rehabilitating the Lagos-Kano railway, which has assisted in boosting commercial activities between northern and southern Nigeria (Okeoguale, 2017:170).

During the period of 1999-2007 trade statistics have shown that the percentage of visible imports and exports between the two countries has continued to increase.

Table 4 shows that India exports to Nigeria have grew from \$293.71 million in 1999-2000 to \$544.68 million in 2004-2005 and \$903.48 million in 2006-2007.The balance of trade has been in Nigeria’s favour, due to the large Indian imports of crude oil .India is the largest importer of Nigeria crude oil after the United States of America and Spain (Indian business 2006).India has also emerged as the fourth largest destination for Nigeria’s non-oil exports (Abubakar & Shehu, 2019:47-50).The major India’s imports from Nigeria include crude oil , metal scrap, aluminum, wood, hides, Cashew nuts, iron and steel, cotton, gum Arabic are among the major trading items that India imports from Nigeria (Ibrahim & Shehu 2016)

Statistics of bilateral trade value in Us & million between Nigeria – India

Nigeria imports from India	200-2004	2004-2005	2005-2006	2006-2007
	565.49	544.68	874.03	904.48

Indian imports from Nigeria	75.64*	48.40*	72.46*	7026.93
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Source: India High commission, Abuja (2011).

Note* Excluding oil imports figures.

India's imports of crude oil from Nigeria

Year	Quantity	Value in us & million
1999-2000	15.450	2597.7
2000-2001	12.570	2140.4
2001-2002	11.320	2001.9
2002-2003	11.578	2389.0
2003-2004	11.074	2393.0

Source: India High Commission, Abuja, Nigeria (2008)

Other Indian Companies involved in Trade and Investments Activities in other sectors of Nigerian Economy.

The economic relations between Nigeria and India goes beyond oil trade to include investment activities in retail business ,telecommunication ,health ,steel ,transport and security .According to Indian high commissioner in Abuja ,more than 100 Indian companies have investments in the country .

Indians are involved gravely in Nigeria's retail business and owned a number of super stores in Nigeria major cities like Abuja, Ibadan, Kano, Lagos and Port Harcourt. Dana plastics and Dana foods are subsidiaries of Dana groups of companies that are involved in sales of plastics, Danaco full cream milk, rice, sun yum instant Noodles, Dana juice, stallion groups supplies rice chemicals and fertilizers. And chellarms that started with textile trading in 1923, has expanded and diversified into manufacturing, marketing and distribution of full cream milk such as Oldenburger and Real milk. Their products are highly patronized in Nigeria's consumer market (Osondu-oti 2015:114).The retail business has increased the choices available to Nigerian consumers and also created job opportunities for Nigeria citizens.

Telecommunications is another leading enterprise in Nigeria and the nation provides the largest market in Africa continent .This attracted India films to involve in the business with Bharti Airtel investing \$600

million in Nigeria's mobile business when it acquired Zain telecoms Africa business for \$10.76 billion. The company has created job opportunities to Nigerians in its Ibadan branch alone about 600 Nigerian graduates secured employment (Infinites, 2009:49). Indian's involvement in zain telecom has paved way for India to penetrate other aspects of business in the information technology (IT) sector .For instance, the National Institute of Information Technology (NIIT), an Indian training institute was established in Nigeria in 1999 with its office in Lagos. Many Nigerians have benefited from their IT service education (Indian High commission Abuja, 2013). NIIT has 35 centres spread across different states in Nigeria and annually it trains almost 15,000 Nigerians in the following areas: Software development, networking, database certification and multimedia application that prepares them for profitable IT jobs (Osondu-Oti 2015:117).

One of the beneficiaries of NIIT training programme Ahmed Eya stated that:

“The training enable me to set up my own cybercafé business which I provide services such as phone call ,selling of global system of mobile (GSM) and computer accessories , provision of internet access and related services via dedicated computer's other devices” (Eya, oral interview 2020).

There has been a considerable number of Nigerians traveling to India for medical treatment as many of them see India as the most favorable area to undertake

medical treatment (Ogoh, Shaibu & Edegbo, 2015:9:15).The cost –effective medical treatments together with high standards in cardiology, orthopedics, nephrology, oncology and neuro-surgery and favorable climatic conditions, accessibility of herbal medicine and high quality and sophisticated specialty hospitals facilitated medical tourism to India by Nigerians who can afford it (James and Apurva, 2015: 45).

According to the India high commission in Abuja, about 40,000 Nigerians obtained visas yearly, out of which 80% of them are for medicine tourism, education, and other travelers. According to Osahon Enabulele president of Nigeria Medical Association, more than 5000 Nigerian citizens travel to India on a monthly basis for medical treatment (Business Day, 18 March 2013).

Furthermore, India is one of Nigeria's major suppliers of pharmaceuticals. The medical drugs are imported to Nigeria by Indian pharmaceutical firms based in the country at relatively low prices (Ogoh, Shaibu and Edegbo, 2015: 9-16).These results in the domination of Nigerian's pharmaceutical industries by the Indian's products which deepens Nigerian dependency on India. In addition there is a concern on the importation of fake and substandard drugs by Indians to Nigeria. This was supported by Mohammad Yaro Budah a pharmacist and president of pharmaceutical society of Nigeria (PSN) he state that;

“70% of the drugs in Nigeria are fake. It is believed that imported fake and substandard drugs in Nigeria come mainly from India, china, Pakistan, Egypt and Indonesia” (cited in Rauful, 2002:2).

Indian's private hospitals and pharmaceuticals firms have also been involved in providing health infrastructure and facilities to Nigeria. In 2003, the Apollo group of hospitals which was one of the first Indian private hospital that have been providing consultancy services to some hospitals in Nigeria has further expanded the services of training medical

doctors, nurses and other medical personnel. The Indian government through its ITEC programmes provided Nigeria with specialized training in healthcare technologies such as bio- medical types of equipment, and medical informatics and also training on how to handle healthcare technology and clinical equipment. This training includes public administration of healthcare sectors (James and Apurva 2019: 44).Although India contributed to the training of Nigeria's medical personnel that has not address the shortage of medical professionals in the country. Nigerians still travel to India for medical follow up.

The hospitals established in Nigeria by the Indians are out of the reach of common man. Furthermore, the domination of Nigeria's pharmaceutical industries by the Indian's products deepens Nigeria dependence on India.

The steel sector is another area where India provided development assistance to Nigeria. The Hindustan Machine Tools Company of India (HMT) is in partnership with Nigerian machine tools for the country (Kura 2009 1-31).Global Infrastructural Holdings Limited (GIHL) an Indian company was also given the concession to handle the Ajaokuta steel company(iron processing mill) in august 2004. At same period Mr. Pramod Mittal, who is the major shareholder of GHIL was also given concession through his other firm, Ispat industries limited (IIL) to handle the Nigeria iron ore mining company (NIOMCO) at Itakpe.

The memorandum of understanding (MOU) provides for the rehabilitation, generation and management of the steel complex for 10 years. The plant was rehabilitated and started production by November, 2004 with imported billets from Ukraine.In February 2005, the Nigerian government further hand over the delta steel company to GIHL (people's daily 2011:04).By 2006 the GIHL started exporting the products to some West African countries.

According to the management of GIHL;

“Ribbed bars were exported to four west African countries ;as follows 3:800 metric tones to Mauritania , 3:400 metric tonnes to Coted, Voire ,1050 metric tones to Benin Republic and 600 metric tons to mail” (Ajateel ,2006:6).

In addition, Ajaokuta steel company supplied power holding company of Nigeria (PHCN) with 65 MW of electricity. Lokoja, Okene, Benin and surrounding benefited from the company’s 85 megawatts (MW) of electricity generated from the independent. Thermal Power Plant (TPP) (Ajateel, 2006.6) Nigeria realized seventy four million (874) in foreign exchange as a result of the exportation of steel. This help in boosting Nigeria’s foreign exchange. Additionally, GIHL also provides the employment opportunities in Nigeria and foster the transfer of technology (Agbu, 2007:62).

Similarly the leasing opens the opportunities for other Indian companies to invest in the steel sector of Nigeria. For example Dana steel Rolling Mill Company an Indian firm, acquired the Federal government owned Kastina steel Rolling Mill Company in 2006 after the privatization process. The steel company is into production of general purpose steel for construction ,and it is a boost to Nigeria industrialization .The company has an installed capacity of 207 ,000 metric per annum (infinities 2011:56). Aarti steel another Indian company established an ultra-modern wet flus continuous galvanizing line plant covering over 10 acres of land at Ota industrial layout in Ogun State.

The company is into production of full hard galvanized products for the production of corrugated roofing sheets, galvanized planning sheets/coils from 0.12 mm to 0.8 mm (Baghla 2009:36).The Aarti steel products are exported directly to West African countries such as Ghana, Republic of Benin, Senegal, Chad and with indirect exports from Ghana and Senegal to Cameroon, Niger and Burkina Faso by retailers (Baghla, 2011:34). The Company has

generated job opportunities for 750 Nigerians (Infinities, 2009:49)

Indian firms are also involved in power generation projects. Skipper electrical , an Indian power generation company invested in Nigeria’s power in 2004 .The company introduced transformer repair facility and its main clients is the transmission section of the power holding company and other private firms in the country (Infinities 2012:54).The investment of India in the power sector of Nigeria has increased the power supplier in the country .This was also observed by Victoria Akaki director general & Abuja chamber of commerce and industry (ACC) when she stated that;

“India has provided critical support to Nigeria in area like agriculture, power, automobile, pharmaceutical, air travel among others” (Thursday, 19February 2020)

Indian automobile companies have also contributed to development of Nigerian transport system with wide spread use & Tata vehicles, Marticars Bajaji, Three –wheeled vehicles and two wheelers made by TVS motors and Ashok Leyland vehicles and tractors manufactured by Mahindras (Vasudevan, 2010:2).These automobile companies have made impact in the life of many Nigerians. This was collaborated by the representative Grover of TVS motors Indian in Nigeria by stating that;

“Our motorcycles and tricycles, or Keke as they are popularly known, touch the lives of millions of Nigerians everyday taking them to work, school ,places of worship and other places of their daily lives activities and employment generation that our vehicles create”(Grover,2018:43)

Dana group and the stallion are the other Indian companies that are into importation of vehicles into Nigeria. Stallion group has been responsible for importation of Kia vehicles, while Dana group is into importation of vehicles such as Hyundai, Honda and Audi. The Dana Company is also into airline transportation in major cities in Nigeria, such as

Lagos, Abuja and Port Harcourt (Alao, 2011:101). This has contributed to the economic development of Nigeria. Sani Yahaya Official of National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW) Abuja, posit that:

“Indian investment in Nigeria transport sector, has contributed to poverty alleviation in Nigeria, by creating employment for the riders of the motorcycles who earn a daily wages for conveying passengers” (Sani, 2020 Oral-Interview)

Defense relationship between Nigeria and India was reinvigorated in the 1990s with return of civil rule in 1999. This led to the signing of memorandum of understanding in October 2007, by the two countries on defense cooperation, covering areas such as defense training, capacity building, equipment support, sharing expertise in counterterrorism and counter insurgency (Kumar 2021:3). As a result of the agreement, some Nigeria military officers and soldiers received training on combating terrorism and urban guerrillas. Owuna (2020) stated that the training consists of:

“Security and strategic studies, defence management, artillery, electronics, mechanical, marine and aeronautical engineering, anti-marine warfare and logistics management (Owuna, 2020: Oral interview).

Similarly, the Indian government assisted Nigeria with military hardware worth over \$1 million. (Kura, 2009:3-9). India also installed IT equipment at Nigeria Defense Academy (NDA), Command Staff College (CSC) Jaji and the National War College (NWC) Abuja. This is to enable the colleges to catch up with the present –day means of communications (Abonyi, 2007), and equally, some of Nigeria armour and personnel carriers are of TATA India made vehicles, the defense cooperation is being extended to include a supply of armament and ammunition, helicopters, trainer aircraft, fast attack patrol many boats, and Nigeria Navy has a large number of them among the collection of their fleet (Abubakar,

2010:129-143). Military relationship between Nigeria and India has continued particularly in the area of training Nigeria armed forces to catch up with its sophisticated equipment.

The training and installation of IT equipment by Indian government has further strengthened Nigeria military. However, engaging Indian in installation of IT equipment and reprofessionalism of the military is an infringement on the national security. Ogbere (2020) posits that:

“In installing sophisticated communication equipment and re-professionalization of Nigeria armed forces is not only making Nigeria armed forces dependent on India but a threat to national security” (Ogbere, 2020 Oral interview)

India -Nigeria Agricultural Relations 1999 – 2007

The development of agriculture and food security is of high priority to the Nigerian government under Obasanjo as this sector employs a large percentage of the Nigerian labor force and it contributes to the gross domestic product (GDP). Therefore, the quest for food sufficiency, diversification of the country's sources of foreign exchange, creating jobs for the unemployed population and expanding its development aid relations. In 2000 Nigeria sought external Investments such as India's Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) to help meet this target and generate employment and raise productivity. (Modi 2010:123). Indian investors responded to the call from the Nigerian government to invest in the Nation's agricultural sector in order to raise the productivity of farmers, raise the income level and eradicate poverty in the long run.

Among the Indian companies that invested in the Nigeria agricultural sector are the “Olam Group” and “Popular Farms and Mills Ltd” a subsidiary of the Stallion Group of companies with the Nigerian headquarters in Kano. The companies cultivated thousands of hectares of land, built mills and machinery, provided farmers in 16 Nigerian States with new improved rice seedlings, and engaged

thousands of farmers in regular training enhancing employment and reinvigorating communities in the country. The support given by these Indian companies has led to an increase in rice productivity, food security, job creation and saving foreign exchange (Ugbudian, 2020:138-150).

The “Olam Group” operate mainly in Nassarawa, Niger and Taraba state while “Popular Farms and Mills Limited” area of operations covers 16 States including Kano, Kaduna, Yobe, Kebbi, kastina, Abuja, Niger, Benue Taraba Adamawa and Borno. “Popular farms and Mills limited” distributed not less than 100 bags of the rice seedlings to Farmers and trained many of them in Yola Adamawa state. According to the director of the company Pandian balamurugan stated that:

“Such activity was in the Spirit of the bilateral agricultural cooperation between India and Nigeria and the main objective of the gesture was to boost their local rice production. (Ugbudian, 2020 138:150”.

Balamurugan further stated that the aim of the initiative was not only to reduce the importation of rice but to eliminate poverty among rural farmers and to motivate youths to the agricultural business. This made them to support rice farmers as well as farmers’ cooperatives to increase rice production. The company has supported 5,000 farmers in 16 states of the country. One of the beneficiaries of the “Popular Farms and Mills Limited” a rice farmer in Kano Maigida Usman stated that:

“The assistance of popular farms and Mills Limited is not only training and supply of good seedlings but they also buy my products, and this made the rice farming business becoming lucrative (Usman oral interview July 20th 2020).” Similarly, Mahesh Nimje, the officer in charge of Farm Project “Olam” in Rukubi in Nasarawa, state stated that the company is highly involved in contributing to the rice sufficiency in food security in the country. One of the rice farmers

that benefited from the support offered, Rose James pointed out that:

Rice farming has become a big business due to the incentives and training provided by the Olam Group (James oral interview July 25th 2020).

The Investments of Indian companies in Nigeria agricultural sector have enhance rice production and improvement in social and economic status of Nigeria. However, this made Nigerian farmers to depend on Indian technology and seedlings instead of improving their own seedlings and technology.

Conclusion

From the discussion above, it is noted that after the cold war, development aid relations between Nigeria and India has witnessed a shift from idealistic ideology, to realistic pro- market economic ideology. This was as a result of the 1991 economic reform policies that attract investment and trading relationships with several African countries, particularly Nigeria after its return to democratic rule in 1999. The paper pointed out that India is interested in gaining access to energy (oil) and raw materials for its industries, and access to overseas market for its industrial goods and outlet for reinvestment of its surplus capital, and using Nigeria as export base for its goods to neighboring African countries. The study also found out that, the Indian trade and investment activities created job opportunities which Indian nationals benefited more than Nigerians because of their expertise. It was also revealed that the onesidness of the relationship has hampered the development of Nigerian. This is because Nigeria import manufactured goods from India, while it exports to India are mainly primarily commodities. This was as a result of their technological advancement and economic potency of India place it in an advantageous position, and this led to the flooding of Nigerians market with cheap imported goods. Thus, Nigerian producers are forced to go out of business. It has been noted that, instead of India trade and investment activities to facilitate the socio-

economic development of Nigeria, it further undermined the development of the country.

From the above findings and conclusions, the paper recommends that the current development aid relation between Nigeria and India is asymmetric in nature, and it is a threat to the sustainable socio-economic development in Nigeria. Therefore, for

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Nigeria to benefit meaningfully from the engagements with India, the relationship has to be restructured to allow for transparency and equal opportunity. This can be done through negotiation between Nigeria and India by the institutions that handle foreign policy.

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